

Stability Constants of σ -Bonded Dialkyltin(IV) Cation with *N*-(2,5-Xylyl)-2-mercaptoacetamides

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The successive stability constants of the complexes of *N*-(2,5-xylyl)-2-mercaptoacetamide with various σ -bonded dialkyltin(IV) cations have been determined in dioxane-water mixture (75%, v/v) at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$ and constant ionic strength $\mu = 0.1 M$ (NaCl) by adopting the pH-titration technique of Irving and Rossotti¹.

Results and Discussion

From the pH titration curves the values $\bar{n}_a$ (the average number of protons attached per ligand molecule), $\bar{n}$ (the average number of ligand ions attached per metal ion), and pL (free ligand exponent) were obtained adopting the Irving-Rossotti technique¹. The various methods (interpolation at half $\bar{n}$ value, least-square method and correction term method) were used to compute stability constants. The values are in good agreement with each other and the average values are reported in Table 1. The maximum value of $\bar{n}$ obtained in the pH region where hydrolysis of metal ions is negligible, is between 1.5 and 2.0, which revealed that metal-ligand ratio in the complexes is 1:2. A comparison of $\log \beta_2$ values reveals the following order of metal chelate stabilities: $\{(CH_3)_2SnCl_2\} > \{(C_2H_5)_2SnCl_2\} > \{(n-C_4H_9)_2SnCl_2\}$, which is in conformity with the Irving-Williams order².

Experimental

All the chemical were of A.R. grade. The ligands and (2,5-xylyl)-2-mercaptoacetamide were synthesised by the reported method³. Dioxane was purified by the standard procedure¹. Dioxane-water (3:1, v/v) was used in preparing metal salt, ligand and NaCl solutions.

The pH-titrations were performed with an ECIL 823 pH meter using glass electrode and saturated calomel electrode (SCE). Titrations performed in a titration cell maintained at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$. The electrodes

were calibrated using potassium hydrogen phthalate (pH = 4) and borate buffer (pH = 9.27) and checked before and after each titration. Two sets of titrations were performed – one with the ligand solution and the other with the ligand solution containing dialkyltin dichloride. Change in pH was recorded as a function of the volume of NaOH added. The following solutions were used: (i) 10 ml of 0.05 M ligand + 20 ml of 0.25 M NaCl + 19.5 ml of dioxane-water mixture (75%, v/v) and (ii) 10 ml of 0.05 M ligand + 10 ml of 0.0125 M dialkyltin-dichloride + 20 ml of 0.25 M NaCl + 10 ml of dioxane-water (75%, v/v).

TABLE I—STEPWISE STABILITY CONSTANTS OF VARIOUS COMPLEXES

Temp $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$, $\mu = 0.1 M$ (NaCl)	$\{(CH_3)_2SnCl_2\}$	$\{(C_2H_5)_2SnCl_2\}$	$\{(n-C_4H_9)_2SnCl_2\}$
	<i>Interpolation at half $\bar{n}$ values</i>		
$\log K_1$	12.91	12.91	12.95
$\log K_2$	8.40	8.11	7.85
$\log \beta_2$	21.31	21.02	20.84
<i>Correction term method</i>			
$\log K_1$	12.92	12.88	12.90
$\log K_2$	8.41	8.10	7.91
$\log \beta_2$	21.33	20.98	20.81
<i>Least-square method</i>			
$\log K_1$	12.91	12.88	12.91
$\log K_2$	8.44	8.11	7.86
$\log \beta_2$	21.35	20.99	20.77

In the first titration, the titrant NaOH was of strength 0.5 M, whereas in the second one the strength of NaOH was 0.1 M.

References

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